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Report on User Evaluation

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Publishable Summary

The GoTriple platform will help social sciences and humanities (SSH) research in Europe to gain visibility. The collaborative tool enables researchers to discover and reuse SSH data across disciplinary and language boundaries, and also find other researchers and projects. GoTriple provides all the necessary means to build interdisciplinary projects and develop large-scale scientific missions. It will thus increase the economic and societal impacts of SSH resources. GoTriple will be a dedicated service of the OPERAS Research Infrastructure with potential to become a strong service in the [EOSC marketplace](#). The European Commission has funded the TRIPLE project under the Horizon 2020 framework with approx. 5.6 million Euros for a duration of 42 months, starting in 2019 and finishing in March 2023

This final version of Deliverable 3.6 follows an interim version that was submitted by Month 30 of the project (March 2022). The deliverable details the key aspects of the methodology for the GoTriple platform evaluation with the users and reports on some of the most important results of this work. The goal of the evaluation work was to improve the usability of the platform ahead of its final release at the end of the project. The work conducted for this purpose included several Think-Aloud tests done remotely with users, two questionnaires (one done in the early phase of the platform release, and a final satisfaction questionnaire) and a quantitative evaluation with metrics and funnels, conducted with analytics tools. The methods selected were used to ensure that the GoTriple platform could meet the end-user needs, in terms of usability. This work has allowed the project consortium to make several improvements to the user interface and to establish as well a permanent evaluation tool for after the funding period (the user satisfaction questionnaire). In summary, this deliverable shares the key results of the evaluation work for both the qualitative and quantitative evaluation of usability as well as the work done for the creation of a lasting solution for measuring user satisfaction, beyond the funding period. This is the last and final deliverable of the TRIPLE project Work Package 3 “Co-Design and User Research”.

1 INTRODUCTION

The goal of this final iteration of Deliverable 3.6 is to report on the methodology planned by the project for the user evaluation of the GoTriple platform and to present some of the key results of this evaluation. T3.6 is the last Task of Work Package 3, devoted to the user research and the codesign for the creation of GoTriple. The evaluation completes the circle of the user research which started with the gathering of the user needs in T3.1, during the initial phase of the project. It then proceeded with a phase of codesign with users (in Tasks 3.2, 3.3 and 3.4), to refine the needs and envision design solutions for the platform. Then it concludes with improving the usability of the GoTriple design and assessing whether the platform meets the user needs and the extent in which users can achieve their intended goals with GoTriple. This assessment is indeed done through an evaluation.

An interim version of D3.6, with initial evaluation results with a focus on the user testing, was submitted in March 2022 (M30). The purpose of the interim deliverable was to define the methodology and to provide initial evaluation knowledge. This final version brings an increased level of detail on the user testing results conducted on GoTriple and reports on the final results of this work.

Task 3.6 “Conduction of User Evaluation” aimed to evaluate with end-users the GoTriple platform, from a social-interactional perspective. The plan for the evaluation was based on three levels of action:

1. A qualitative usability evaluation of interfaces and functionalities of the platform
2. A quantitative usability evaluation via metrics/measurements made from monitoring the platform usage
3. An evaluation of user ‘satisfaction’ towards the GoTriple platform solution carried out using a questionnaire.

The goal of this task - according to the project description - was thus to **provide the consortium with actionable information for improving the final release of GoTriple** at Month 42 (with a particular focus on improving the user interface) as well as to provide additional information about the status of some of the project objectives, in particular in relation to the user satisfaction.

In the first iteration of D3.6, we focused on the description of the methodology and presented some initial results for the first two items of the evaluation. This final version re-proposes the methodology with refined details and, most importantly, it presents the final results for the first two items/objectives of the task, and presents some examples of how the GoTriple interface has been improved as result of the testing conducted with the users. The satisfaction questionnaire has been prepared and is now included in the platform interface. However we have only limited responses so far (6 completions), which is not as of yet sufficient to draw insights. This is likely due to the fact that the user community is still in its nascent phase, and therefore the numbers do not yet support a high level of completion of the questionnaire.

For the qualitative usability evaluation, the WP3 team decided to adopt a Think-Aloud protocol to work with the users. The Think-Aloud technique is discussed in the methodology section of this deliverable. Moreover, in late 2021 the TRIPLE project partnered with another EU project called ReachOut which has developed a tool/questionnaire for user evaluation of digital products. We have helped them with testing their tool, while at the same time gathering an initial set of observations for our own evaluation of GoTriple. For the quantitative evaluation, we used analytics tools in order to derive usability measures, in particular, by assessing funnels. These two approaches (qualitative and quantitative) thus intersect, with the first one working with a small number of users gathering in-depth observations, and the second one working on a larger pool of users (potentially all the platform users to date) gathering high-level observations. Both these approaches will be presented in detail later in the deliverable. Lastly, for the satisfaction questionnaire we have created an online questionnaire which is directly available from the GoTriple homepage. This aims at measuring high-level user satisfaction of core functionalities and services of GoTriple. Again the structure and rationale for the questionnaire will be presented later. This questionnaire was also developed with the aim to have it functioning beyond the funding period and to operate a constant monitoring of the user satisfaction.

To complement the planned methodology, some additional activities have been initiated, which will be briefly described later. These include the creation of a bug/issue reporting form and a UX (User Experience) board (Trello board) to record the emerging issues that needed attention. This last item of action has been essential for passing the results of the qualitative evaluation to the project partner (Net7) in charge of the interface design. Thus issues identified during the user testing could be addressed in a timely fashion and be reflected on the platform interface design.

2 Usability Evaluation

The work on the evaluation of the platform has been organised around the platform feature releases. The team had to extend the deadline for the task and related deliverable, since the release of some of the core platform components has been affected by some delays associated with the complexity of the development activities. This has consequently required adjusting the evaluation plan that was devised originally, and proposing a more flexible approach adjusting deadlines and work-activities. This also has likely had some impact on the user satisfaction questionnaire completion. A very early release of the platform was done in the last part of 2021, allowing users to explore the basic search functionalities of the platform. By late Spring 2022 a Beta release was available, with more functionalities, including some of the dashboards, but effectively a near-to-final version of the platform only became available for testing around the beginning of September 2022 (including all the dashboards, the user profiles etc.). Additional components were released after this date (e.g. additional features of the profiles). Therefore, much of the evaluation took place from after August 2022, and only some initial and interim work was conducted before that month, part of which was reported in the interim D3.6 (up until March 2022). Moreover, T3.6 has been affected by the roll-out of the user engagement

strategy. A strategy for onboarding users had been defined during 2022 within WP8, but its full roll-out has been delayed because the consortium needed to ensure the adoption of the right timing between inviting users to register and having the core functionalities available (therefore with a possible effective start only in late 2022). Indeed, it would have been a risky strategy to invite users to register to the platform whilst only some functionalities were available, with a risk of alienating early adopters with an unfinished product. This delay in the roll-out of the user engagement has impacted in particular the work on the satisfaction questionnaire, as we would expect this to be completed by users arriving on GoTriple as results of the user engagement, or by users who have been using the platform for some time.

While during the interviewing phase (Task 3.1) and the codesign phase of the project (Tasks 3.2, 3.3 and 3.4) several users have been involved in the process of conceiving the shape of GoTriple, it was deemed of fundamental importance for the success of the GoTriple to ensure that current and future users will be able to use the platform and especially its interface to achieve their every-day research goals. This is where usability and its evaluation become fundamental.

Nielsen [1] defined usability as *“a quality attribute that assesses how easy user interfaces are to use”*. This is a known and widely used definition in the literature that captures the task at hand for the GoTriple consortium in T3.6, which was assessing (i.e. evaluating) how easy it is for our users to use the platform interface to achieve their intended goals (e.g. the discovery of resources). Normally usability evaluation concentrates on measuring aspects related to whether the user can easily learn the interface, how and when they may encounter errors or blocked paths in achieving their goals, if the overall interface design is appealing or pleasant for the user, how easy it is for them to achieve their goal and if they can do so efficiently and also if they can memorise the interface and how to use it when returning to the platform.

During the evaluation of usability, testing activities are thus normally conducted directly with the support of the users. These users are required to conduct some tasks with the digital product (i.e. the GoTriple platform in our case) during which it is possible to evaluate whether and how well these tasks are performed and/or if there are problems emerging. These activities are also called user-testing.

By working on the usability and its evaluation, the research for Task 3.6 aimed therefore to deliver relevant knowledge for assessing whether the GoTriple designed interface serves well the users (thus meeting their needs) and provides insights for improving it, with an eye of having an usable solution for after the funding period. Figure 1 shows the process in a simplified way, with the usability work intended to deliver insights to improve the platform’s interface.

FIGURE 1 - SIMPLIFIED VERSION OF THE PROCESS OF THE RESEARCH FOR TASK 3.6

There are several potential techniques that can be used to assess the usability of a (digital) product and in current research there often is not a common way to classify them. These can range from evaluations that are conducted by expert evaluators (for example using pre-specified heuristics), down to evaluations that are almost entirely driven by users. The most commonly used heuristics are those defined by Nielsen in 1994 [2] where expert reviewers understand the heuristics and can identify issues that conflict with them.

These tests can be moderated and unmoderated. Techniques for evaluation can also be quantitative and qualitative or can use different ways to capture the required data, for example, questionnaires, video recordings or analytics. For simplicity, in the writing phase of the project, we decided to break down our usability evaluation into qualitative and quantitative, meaning for us that we wanted a set of in-depth and rich observations (qualitative) as well as more high level and numerical observations (quantitative). Potential options for methodologies were indicated in the Task descriptions. Our choices for the evaluation approach and the methods will be discussed in later sections.

Overall for the usability evaluation, we have set to measure the following main user goal: **how well the users can perform their discovery activities using the GoTriple platform**. This goal pretty much informed all the work conducted for this task and the usability was measured against the capacity for the users to achieve this goal. To carry out this evaluation, we have used both moderated and unmoderated remote usability tests.

2.1 Creation of the User Testing Group

To support the qualitative usability evaluation activities, it was decided between the coordinator, the WP3 leader, partner Net7 (the lead interface designer) and the WP8 leader that it would be very useful to have a group of active and motivated SSH researchers who would be willing to be involved in the user testing and other related activities for the task. Several meetings were held (involving WP3, WP8 and WP1) to ensure that a large enough pool of contacts could be gathered. The mailing list created by WP1 (with initial contacts gathered from the User Questionnaire conducted as part of Task 3.1) was utilised along with social media to raise awareness about the group and to encourage people to sign up. Moreover, the list of participants of the first TRIPLE conference and the OPERAS Forums were used to further recruit potentially interested researchers as user testers. Using these communication channels, we have created a group of 63 people of varying SSH disciplines and dispersed geographic locations. This has proved to be an invaluable resource for this work, especially for the Think-Aloud/qualitative user testing described below. Many participants to the qualitative evaluation indeed came from this list and only in late 2022 we had to resort to finding additional contacts for the evaluation through the networks of the project partners.

2.2 Qualitative Usability Evaluation Methods

To see how users actually interact with the GoTriple platform and to ensure any usability issues are captured, it is important to carry out User testing activities. The use of qualitative evaluation is important in this context as qualitative inquiry is non manipulative, inductive, and discovery oriented, and allows one to focus on the meaning of behaviour, and the context within which it occurs. In the following sections 2.2.1 and 2.2.2 we share the methods adopted in the context of this task to identify usability issues encountered on the GoTriple interface and then discuss our findings in section 3.

2.2.1 Think-Aloud

The Think-Aloud method [3] (also referred to as verbal protocols or verbal reporting) is a commonly used and popular method where the participants are asked to verbalise their thoughts as they move through the user interface¹. It is a very commonly used technique and has the advantage of being relatively simple [4], although [5] highlights that it can add to the cognitive load of the user especially if the task is demanding [6]. It is believed that the Think-Aloud method helps to identify the cognitive processes responsible for the users' behaviour [7]. A useful paper by Nielsen et al [8] reflects on the Think-Aloud method, and highlights the fact that *'users think faster than they can speak and their thoughts are much more complex than they can verbalize'*. The paper argues that the success of the Think-Aloud method is dependent on the effectiveness of the recording method and

¹ <https://www.nngroup.com/articles/thinking-aloud-the-1-usability-tool/>

subsequent analysis. Furthermore, the paper argues that the method is best used in conjunction with other techniques (as we have done here for the evaluation of the GoTriple platform, where alongside the Think-Aloud we have conducted a quantitative evaluation).

The Think-Aloud method is a technique that does not require the user to retrospectively reflect on their interaction with the system but records their thoughts while actually performing the task (whereas the method we used for the ReachOut survey relied on recollection - see later). The advantages of the Think-Aloud method is that it is relatively cheap (no special equipment is needed); it is Robust, Flexible (able to be used at any stage), Easy to learn and Convincing [2]. It allows participants to report everything that goes through their minds while carrying out a given task, and they are asked not to interpret or analyse their thinking. However, it is not always easy to run a monologue while carrying out a task. Therefore, the moderator will from time to time prompt the participant to keep talking as they carry out the given task.

The Think-Aloud method is a moderated usability test, and for our evaluations, it was undertaken remotely due to the geographical distance with the users (as they are all located across Europe). We engaged with users via Teams or Zoom, making use of the screen share functionality. Users visited the GoTriple website whilst sharing their screen (with the session being recorded) and were then asked to go through a series of predefined tasks set by the moderator. A session would last around 45-60 minutes and while the user is carrying out the tasks they are asked to 'Think-Aloud' and explain to the moderator the actions they are making, their intentions and anything they find surprising or frustrating during the process. We developed a protocol for the users to follow that allows them to use the different GoTriple features in a methodical way. The protocol was a list of tasks to achieve rather than specific instructions of how to use the platform. In this way, we can see if the GoTriple interface is intuitive or not, given that the testers have had little or no previous interaction with the platform.

The following protocol was used to moderate the user testing of the features of the GoTriple platform.

TABLE 1. USABILITY EVALUATION PROTOCOL-GUIDE

Task	Moderator's questions	Participants actions
Setting the scene: Introduction of the participant	Tell me about yourself and what you do for a living	Introduce themselves and what they do for a living
Onboarding the user: I want you to register as a user in the GoTriple platform	Let me know: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Your thought as you go through the interface <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What are you trying to do? ● What are you looking for? 	Follow the necessary procedure and register as a user in the GoTriple platform <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Open browser · Navigate to site · Click sign in to register · Enter username in the username field

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The decision you are making <p>Tell me when you are stuck or confused as you move through the interface</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enter password in the password field <p>Login into your GoTriple platform</p>
<p>Authorship claim: Take a look at the suggested documents and accept authorship of the project or research works.</p>	<p>Same question as in 2 above</p>	<p>Find their project or research works and accept the ownership of them</p>
<p>Testing other interface: Take a good look at the platform and explore as much as you can</p>	<p>Same question as in 2 above</p>	<p>Use the search interface and explore the platform</p>

For our user testing, informed consent forms and information sheets were sent to the participants in advance of the planned session, explaining the procedure and checking that participants were happy for the session to be recorded. The testers were also made to feel comfortable at the start of the session and it was explained that it was not their performance that was being evaluated, but the platform, and that their feedback is invaluable in making improvements to the platform.

During the period December 2021 to July 2022, we have conducted some preliminary (n=6) Think-Aloud tests on the Beta version of GoTriple. With the subsequent release of a near-to-final version of the platform in August/September 2022, we conducted a more extensive activity of testing with the approach (n=20). Usability issues identified during this work were passed on to the UI designers using a Trello board (see later section 4.2), where issues could be evaluated from an UI perspective and prioritised. Notes on any difficulty encountered by the tester were made during the session by the facilitator. After the session, the video recording was reviewed, and to help highlight any problems encountered by the users to the developers, screenshots of areas of interest were made from the session recording; these have been included alongside the notes to illustrate the area of focus. The key results of the user tests are reported in section 3.2 of the deliverable.

2.2.2 The ReachOut Collaboration

In the final part of 2021, the TRIPLE project had the opportunity to partner with another EU project called [ReachOut](#). The ReachOut project had the goal to deliver tools to improve the

market readiness of digital products. In particular, ReachOut had developed a standard questionnaire for the Beta Testing of platforms (using both open questions and some scales). We were invited to use this tool and utilise their support. The advantage for TRIPLE was that we received their support in setting up a small testing campaign (with also rewards potentially offered to participants directly by ReachOut) as well as, more importantly, that we collected an initial set of actionable usability observations. We conducted a small campaign in the period 28 October 2021 to 28 November 2021. Twenty-eight users participated in this campaign, with a total of 20 fully completed questionnaires being submitted.

The ReachOut platform works by providing a framework for beta testing and defining potential scenarios that the users have to conduct. After the scenarios are completed, users are required to fill in a questionnaire, containing some quantitative measures (mostly in the form of Likert scales) as well as qualitative fields where the users can write their observations. While the ReachOut platform had a set of predefined questions, we have modified these questions to make them more suitable for the GoTriple testing. Figure 2 shows the presentation of the GoTriple - ReachOut campaign, outlining the intended objectives and the specific requirements, in particular the need for the testers to be (ideally) SSH researchers.

Beta tester level:

Beginner, Intermediate, Advanced

Campaign objectives

The Triple Project has released a beta version of its Discovery platform GoTriple, with an initial set of features. More features will be added in the coming months, till March 2022. The aim of this campaign is to test the beta platform, pick up any usability issues and improve the platform so that when we release the final version, it will meet the needs of the end-users.

Requirements for this campaign

Ideally, you will have a background in Social Science and Humanities and have knowledge of searching for information and research material, such as scientific publications.

Beta test instructions and scenario

The beta version of the software can be accessed at <https://www.gotriple.eu>

FIGURE 2 - PRESENTATION OF THE GOTRIPLE/REACHOUT CAMPAIGN

Figure 3 shows the “testing scenarios” we have prepared for the campaign. At the time of testing, a limited set of functionalities were available in the Beta version of GoTriple. Nonetheless, we envisioned 3 testing scenarios: 1) related to the discovery of a publication 2) related to the production of a Knowledge Map and 3) related to the production of a

Streamgraph. Each testing scenario had a predefined set of steps that users were required to perform, prior to completing the related questionnaire.

Instructions:

Test 1: Goal to find which authors published the most on a topic

1. Go to the GoTriple Beta testing platform via the above web address
2. Enter a search term of your choice
3. Browse the results of the search
4. Select the 'Visual' View of results
5. Explore the visual view elements
6. Refine the results to show papers from just one of the disciplines provided
7. Clear the refinement to show results from all disciplines again
8. Find which authors published the most on this topic
9. Click on an author name to view other publications from this author.

Test 2: Goal to produce a Knowledge Map and examine it

1. Make a new search on 'Society + Covid'
2. Refine the results to show only papers published in 2020
3. Clear the 2020 selection
4. Find book chapters published on this topic (same search Society + Covid)
5. Clear the book chapter selection to return to the overall search list
6. Create a Knowledge Map for this search (be patient it takes a bit of time!)
7. Examine the knowledge map and see the grouped publications
8. Return to Home Page

Test 3 Goal: Examine Disciplines and produce a Streamgraph

1. Examine the Disciplines Tab - try clicking on any that are of interest to you
2. View a list of publications from a discipline
3. Use the filter to refine the results shown
4. Return to the Home page
5. Make a new search on the term 'Co-design'
6. View the Streamgraph for this search
7. Examine the results of the Streamgraph
8. Visit the GOTRIPLE tab to view project information

Incentives

Beta Testers will be offered to be added to the ReachOut "Hall of Fame", will automatically take part in the ReachOut Super Prize, and 24 randomly chosen Beta Testers with a fully completed questionnaire will be awarded a money prize in recognition.

FIGURE 3 - THE 3 TESTING SCENARIOS FOR THE REACHOUT/TRIPLE CAMPAIGN

The GoTriple/ReachOut questionnaire encompassed a number of Likert scales type of questions (whose specific items will be presented in the Results section) measuring easiness of use and other aspects, but it was otherwise composed of open questions, where users could provide textual details about their experience. Examples of questions included were, for instance:

- In your view, was there anything confusing in using the GoTriple beta platform? What was difficult when using the platform?

- Do you have any further comments on anything you encountered during this initial test that you would like to tell us? Please feel free to be as detailed as possible.
- or Could you elaborate on your answer? [after having asked if they used the platform beyond the testing scenarios]

These open and encompassing formulations for the questions were intended to gather qualitative details of the user experience in terms of usability of the Beta version of the platform, which would otherwise escape from the Likert scales. We will present some key qualitative insights in the results section.

2.3 Quantitative Usability Evaluation

For the quantitative usability evaluation, the method relied on the use of software that is able to track the actions of users and produce analytics. The work conducted during the early part of the task (up until March 2022) was that of establishing a set of requirements for supporting this work once the full platform would be released. Moreover, work had - in the early phase of the task - been conducted in order to assess different analytics/tracking platforms to find which would be most suitable for our purposes. During the evaluation, we concentrated on tracking events, and the building of funnels (which will offer a direct observation of the platform use). These aspects will be described in the following pages, but more space will be given to funnels as they will be the primary means of the quantitative evaluation.

From the internal discussion, we evaluated that two platforms would be suitable for our goals of collecting the relevant analytics:

- Matomo
- Mixpanel

Matomo was already in use by GoTriple as a general analytics platform and it would be suitable for some of our evaluation purposes. Mixpanel has already been widely used by the lead design partner (Net7) and it offers the advantage that it is a tool designed with the purposes of optimising an interface for achieving specific objectives such as conversion and retention. Much of the usability evaluation relied consequently on the use of Mixpanel.

2.3.1 Event tracking and Funnels

Event tracking

One fundamental element for the evaluation based on analytics is the capacity to track events triggered by the users on the frontend interface, for example, the clicks on buttons. This is usually an important component for understanding user behaviour and assessing high-level aspects of usability. Amongst other things, event tracking allows the designers to understand

what the user does when they land on a page of the platform i.e. what is (or are) the main actions that they perform on a page and also to know if they are performing the kind of actions that were intended from the design. Event tracking can then be used to see the occurrence of events over time (e.g. the number of times users click on the sign-up button) and in particular to build funnels.

Funnels

Funnel analysis² allows designers to observe how users are actually interacting on a platform. A funnel is a type of analysis that allows designers to understand what actions are taken by the user in order to achieve the desired goal. For example, we track the onboarding flow, from the first click on the Sign-Up button, to the completion of the user registration, tracking all the steps in the middle (those that occur on GoTriple). This allows us to understand if there are some steps in the user experience of this funnel where users interrupt their journey (that highlight some usability issues or bugs). Any potential pattern of interruption would thus require investigation and intervention on the interface or on the software.

By tracking each step the users take on GoTriple, in relation to predefined funnels, while trying to complete a task and achieve a potential desired goal (e.g. the registration), we can extract two main pieces of information:

1. **The overall "conversion" of a task:** this provides a quantitative value of how many users start a task, and manage to complete it. A good example is how many users will click on the "Sign Up" button, and which percentage of them will actually complete the signup and onboarding process.
2. **Each step of the funnel:** this allows to investigate with more accuracy at which steps of the funnel users find obstacles and can't proceed (drop-off). The steps with the higher drop-off rate are indicators of usability issues or technical problems that prevent the user from completing the task.

The overall conversion of a funnel is the first indicator we look at. If we notice a drop in the value with time or a value that's below our expectations, we then observe the funnel steps in more detail to see in which phase of the journey users find the most difficulties. In fact, the points of a higher drop-off in the funnel are where we have to focus our attention to understand what can be changed to improve that value.

After having defined the most critical steps we want to monitor, it is possible to:

1. Test the funnel to understand if there are technical issues that prevent some users from completing the task. For this investigation, it is useful to check on Mixpanel the type of device and browser used by users that can't complete the funnel.
2. Make a usability analysis of the dropoff step and see if there are evident usability issues that can be fixed.

² See <https://mixpanel.com/blog/introduction-to-analytics-funnel-analysis/>

After this analysis, a design and development iteration is done to publish an updated version (of e.g. GoTriple). After the new version is released, a new observation period is started during which to check if the new version performs better than the previous. This also includes verifying if the critical drop-off percentage previously identified has improved. If the funnel conversion has worsened, there is a need to revert to the previous version and plan another improvement iteration.

It is difficult to define some absolute values for these conversion metrics: for this reason, we decided to work iteratively and focus attention on the most critical steps in the adopted funnels (see below) and work to improve the user experience (and the metrics) in successive stages.

In terms of work planning, key funnels were created in the second part of 2022, in particular, when the sign-up process and the user profiles were released.

Two main funnels were built in particular, to track the login and registration user flow, as these were considered the two most critical components of the usability in terms of user enrolment and adoption:

1. **Login funnel:** it tracks the user from the click on the LOGIN button to the completed login and lands back on GoTriple.
 - Dropoff in the funnel will reveal if the login process should be improved.
2. **Registration & Onboarding funnel:** It tracks the user from the click on the REGISTRATION button to the completed registration. And it also tracks the accomplishment of the steps required to complete the user profile - Onboarding process.
 - Dropoff in the funnel will reveal if the registration and onboarding process should be improved.

3 RESULTS OF THE GOTRIPLE USER EVALUATION

In the following pages we present key results obtained from the user evaluation. We will start with presenting the results of the initial ReachOut campaign, as chronologically this took place at the beginning of the work. This will be followed by some of the key results of the qualitative evaluation, where we will present some exemplar cases of our findings. We will then present some insights from the quantitative evaluation. Lastly we will describe the user satisfaction questionnaire.

3.1 Results of the Reachout/TRIPLE Campaign

Several useful observations were derived as a result of the ReachOut campaign run in the early stages of this evaluation. It is important to note however that some of the issues that emerged from the users were already planned to be addressed by the releases of GoTriple in March and

August 2022, such as for example the “filter by language” option. Thus some items do not constitute usability problems per se, but mostly features that were not yet available to public users. Nonetheless, we report here the issues as they emerged directly from the research, most of which were then addressed by the new platform releases. These included the following:

Search Issues:

1. The lack of a Constant Search Bar forces the user back to the homepage to make a new search. The search bar is now available on the top-right corner of the interface (See Figure 4)
2. Some information regarding the syntax is required for searching with multiple words

FIGURE 4 - TOP BAR OF THE PLATFORM. ABOVE THE VERSION AVAILABLE BEFORE MARCH 2022 WITH THE SEARCH MISSING. THE ONE BELOW IS THE BAR AS CURRENTLY AVAILABLE WITH THE SEARCH OPTION

Filtering:

3. Not having a ‘filter by language’ option - addressed in the release done March 2022 (see Figure 5)
4. The refinement (filtering) is not intuitive, not filtering when clicking on the filter options. The filter is now easy to use, using the provided facets.
5. If filtering is working, then more feedback is needed to ensure the users know that it has worked. With the releases from August 2022, any action done on the filtering appears at the top of the filtering section.

FIGURE 5 - THE LANGUAGE FILTER, AS AVAILABLE ON THE GOTRIPLE INTERFACE CURRENTLY

Language filter:

6. The testers tried to search with words in French, German, Italian (and English of course) but it was not working optimally. They commented that it is crucial to be able to search in different languages

Navigation/labelling:

7. Not having the link to the author when it is clicked. Profiles were not yet part of the Beta Version of the GoTriple platform, but now from the searches, authors on each publication have their own clickable profile
8. The user was not sure what the 'Projects' tab was, as Projects were not yet harvested on this early version of the platform

Data Sources:

9. It was hard to know if GoTriple gathers only Open Access items or not.

Participating testers also provided a number of **positive comments**, some of which are summarised here:

1. When coming across a relevant publication or a book, the platform provides an interesting way of looking at other publications in the same domain, by the same or different authors, and viewing the history of publications on that topic.
2. The streamgraph and knowledge map make the platform different from what exists in the market. It allows representing information in different (visual) ways, which is easier to perceive.
3. The streamgraphs are particularly interesting to see how the usage of terms evolves over time.
4. The UI is very pleasant; the interface is quite intuitive, and nothing confusing.

A small part of the ReachOut Questionnaire was composed of Likert scales. These were partially adapted from the original ReachOut questionnaires.

Figure 6 shows the response to a Likert scale intended to provide an initial measure of the ease of use and usefulness of the GoTriple Beta and also the attractiveness and understandability of the interface. As we can see overall we have received positive responses to the scale items (in the Strongly Agree and Agree categories). The interface of the GoTriple Beta appears overall easy to use (19 out of 21 positive responses) and easy to understand (20 out of 21) for the majority of respondents. The Beta interface is clearly also very attractive for the majority (15 out of 21), but with also some users remaining uncertain.

FIGURE 6 - INITIAL MEASURES ABOUT THE USER INTERFACE OF THE GO TRIPLE BETA

The questionnaire contained a set of Likert items focusing on the ease of use of the GoTriple Beta. Figure 7 shows the results as well as the items of the scale. Overall we can see positive responses across all the items. A small number of people reported difficulties in making a new search as opposed to making a search from the platform homepage (this corresponds to the information given in the free text response about the lack of a constant search bar and the difficulty in returning back to the homepage to make a new search). For making an initial search (column 2) no difficulty was reported. The difficulties reported in columns 5 (refine by date)

and 7 (filter) also relate to the reports of the filtering not being intuitive or not working correctly in the free-text responses.

How easy

Very Easy Easy Unsure Difficult

FIGURE 7 - INITIAL EASE OF USE MEASURES ABOUT THE USER INTERFACE OF THE GoTRIPLE BETA PLATFORM

We also asked participants to rate two additional items: 1) the stability of the Beta platform (on a scale 1 to 5, with 5 as very stable and 1 as not stable at all) and 2) whether they would likely recommend the use of the Beta to others. As we can see in Figures 7 and 8, overall participants gave us positive responses. The stability was rated 5 by half of participants (n=10) and 4 by another eight participants. Sixteen people gave a positive response to their likelihood of recommending the Beta to others, with four unsure and only one unlikely to recommend it.

FIGURE 8 - INITIAL STABILITY RATING OF THE GOTRIPLE BETA PLATFORM

3.2 Results of the Think-Aloud User Testing

In this section we report some of the results of the qualitative user testing, conducted with the Think-Aloud protocol. We conducted 26 tests in total. During testing, several usability issues were encountered and reported to the design team. In this section we report some key examples of the issues that were identified, in particular showing interface details. Most of these issues have all been addressed on the current GoTriple interface (some examples will be provided in the next pages), whilst others are planned to be addressed. We also report some examples of issues that emerged during the testing that cannot be classed as usability problems, and may be associated with aspects such as metadata quality or underlying software issues.

Some issues found during usability testing are as follows:

- 1. User registration:** There is a long list of information to go through during registration. The user gets frustrated after putting all the required information and the system is still saying that the profile is just 15% complete see Figure 9.

This registration issue was resolved by enabling the user that already has Google or ORCID accounts to register through these means. This method helps to facilitate the process and the percentage of profiles being registered was removed.

FIGURE 9 - INITIAL USER REGISTRATION OF THE GOTRIPLE BETA PLATFORM

- 2. Authorship claim:** As new users register in the platform, the authorship claim window is supposed to suggest some document based on the user's name in order to claim authorship of the documents. Users expected that when no documents are suggested for authorship claim, the system would have just mentioned that there was no document for you to claim authorship. The users also expected to see the "next" button to continue.

FIGURE 10 - AUTHORSHIP CLAIM IN THE PLATFORM

3. The knowledge map:

- Knowledge maps show to the user circles which represent the results of the discovery, and when the user clicks on one of the circles of the knowledge map, the user struggles to go back because the “back to overview” button is not visible. Users recommended making the “back to overview” button more visible.
- If a user refines their search at this point, there is no “ok” button to click and the enter key does not change the search results. Users recommended to have this “ok” button or at least the enter key would work after refining your search.

FIGURE 11 THE KNOWLEDGE MAP OF THE GOTRIPLE BETA PLATFORM, AND THE USABILITY ISSUES IDENTIFIED

- To view projects:** the user expectation is to see all the people involved in a project with their affiliated institutions and also to see the project summary and not GoTriple’s project summary. While it is not possible to retrieve the names of all the people

participating in a project as this information is not directly available (e.g. from CORDIS), the problem with the summary has now been solved.

FIGURE 12 - PROJECT VIEW IN THE PLATFORM

- 5. Conditions of Access:** During search, when a user types in some keywords the search results displays the condition of access. The expectation is to see all the words appear as a label and not as a link as shown in Figure 13 below. However this may be due to how the conditions of access are available from the original source.

FIGURE 13 - CONDITIONS OF ACCESS EXAMPLE OF LINK RATHER THAN LABEL

- 6. Streamgraph/Knowledge map:** There are cite and export buttons below each document. Users get frustrated to see that the export button would just show the Bibtex referencing style and the heading “export this document” is not clickable. Users recommended that the “export this document” should be removed since there is an option of copy and download of the reference at the bottom of the page. To note that the availability of Bibtex only is not a usability issue per se, and currently users can export the citation also as JSON and JSON-LD from the GoTriple search.

FIGURE 14 - STREAMGRAPH VIEW IN THE PLATFORM WITH THE EXPORT OPTION AT THE TIME OF TESTING

From the streamgraph, during a test a user was confused about why the information appeared in different languages. However we need to note that multiple languages use the same or very similar words (e.g. filosofia/philosophy – is a word in both Italian and Portuguese). This may also be dependent upon the fact that publications report the original word in a specific language.

7. **Bug Reporting:** When clicking on the bug report feature the user expected to see a chat at this point (rather than a questionnaire to fill in) to help them to sort out certain issues assuming they should need help. This has recently been addressed with a new feature for bug reporting (added in late 2022), which allows the user to provide additional details within a management system. This is described in detail in section 4.1.

FIGURE 15 - BUG REPORTING AS IT WAS APPEARING AT THE TIME OF TESTING, THIS HAS NOW BEEN MODIFIED

8. Search results:

- a. The early tests revealed that users expected that as they type in the search keywords in English, the search results should all appear in the same language. However, Figure 16 revealed that when a keyword is typed in English, the search results appear in another language. The search results were not related to the search keywords. Therefore, the filtering of the search results required to be upgraded.

FIGURE 16 - SEARCH RESULTS VIEW WITH MULTIPLE LANGUAGES

- b. The users expected the name of the funding scheme to appear in upper case capital and the organisation names should all appear in the upper case capital letter. Users also identified some letters are capitalised when they should not be capitalised as shown in Figure 17. However this may be due to how the material was harvested originally.

FIGURE 17 - SEARCH RESULTS VIEW WITH ISSUES AROUND CAPITAL LETTERS AND NAMES

- c. During a test a user clicked on the publication date graph on the left-hand side of the search dashboard interface. It was expected that the publications would be filtered to show only the date selected, but this did not happen. There was no "Enter" button to confirm the selection that was then typed into the 'From to' Boxes. The filtering did work when the 10 years option was selected. This issue has been addressed and the filtering work. There is no need for a button since the platform automatically updates the graph and the search.

FIGURE 18 - PUBLICATION DATE CHART

After identifying the usability issues, these were sent to the design teams for the system update. The procedure for this is described in section 4.2. Here, in concluding this section we comment with graphical examples of how some of these issues were resolved.

The sign up button

FIGURE 19- SIGN-UP ISSUE REPORTED DURING USABILITY (LEFT) AND SOLUTION (RIGHT)

Looking at Figure 19 the image on the right does not have a sign up button. While onboarding the user, users expected that there should be a sign-up button beside the sign-in button for users to register as a new user, rather than clicking the sign-in button before accessing the sign-up button. These issues were resolved by the design team as shown in the image at the right hand side in Figure 19, where the platform now has the two buttons.

Project description/summary

FIGURE 20- GOTRIPLE'S PROJECT SUMMARY CHANGED TO DESCRIPTION, BEFORE (LEFT) AND AFTER (RIGHT)

One usability issue that emerged was related with the following: users when they click on a project (from the search), expect to see the project summary at the top of the project but rather what was offered was a summary of GoTriple. This is considered an error. The design team were able to update this by putting description instead of GoTriple's project summary see (right side of Figure 20).

Condition of access

FIGURE 21 - CONDITION OF ACCESS AS LINK OR LABEL

Figure 21 shows before and after updating the issue appearing sometimes with the conditions of access as link rather than label (left). This is also an error which has been rectified (right).

Funder: Capitalise the first letter

In Figure 21 (left side) the “f” of the label funder appeared a lower case and the users expected it to appear as capital letter, this has been corrected (right side).

FIGURE 22 - FUNDER WRITTEN IN LOWERCASE CHANGED TO INITIAL CASE CAPITAL

Document filter

Figure 23 shows that (during a test, left side) when the user selected the years from the chart, the expectation was for the system to filter the documents based on the year they had chosen. However, this was not what was happening. This has been addressed (right side of Figure 23).

FIGURE 23 - DOCUMENT FILTERED ACCORDING TO THE YEAR SELECTED

3.3 Results of the Quantitative evaluation and Funnels

Several useful observations for improving the usability of the platform were derived as a result of the funnels created in Mixpanel and described in section 2.3.1 of the deliverable. We will present here two key cases as examples of the insights derived from this approach.

The Login funnel:

The login process for GoTriple takes place via OPERAS-ID (see Figure 24), which to the user appears as an external platform, where users can choose from a set of identification providers (EGI, ORCID or Google) or simply create an account with an email address and password.

FIGURE 24 – THE GOTRIPLE LOGIN VIA OPERAS-ID

FIGURE 25 - LOGIN FUNNEL - ANALYSING THE STEPS USERS TAKE TO LOG INTO THE GOTRIPLE PLATFORM

Even though users must use this external portal for their login/sign-up, the funnel data show that more than 60% of users still manage to complete the process and return to the GoTriple platform (left bar of Figure 25). Thus, we can safely conclude that the login process doesn't need any significant improvements, although we keep monitoring the funnel in order to identify any potential emerging issue. In this case therefore the funnel served as confirmation that usability does not present major issues or problems.

The registration and onboarding funnel

Analytics data from the registration and onboarding funnel shows how many users completed the registration process for GoTriple, how many of them proceeded with the onboarding process and lastly how many users completed all the steps required to set a complete user GoTriple profile.

The specific funnel under consideration facilitated the confirmation of our conclusion regarding the Login funnel. The registration process follows a comparable route, with users required to navigate through the OPERAS-ID platform in order to complete their registration. Figure 26 provides a visual representation of this funnel and demonstrates a dropdown percentage of 62.5% (central bars), indicating that the majority of users were able to successfully complete the action.

FIGURE 26 - GoTRIPLE REGISTRATION AND ONBOARDING FUNNEL

In this funnel we observed how many of the registered users completed all the steps of the Onboarding process designed in 3 steps to help them to complete their profile details.

Therefore the funnel shows us that:

62,5% of the users came back to GoTriple, after completing the registration.

40% of them managed to complete the first two steps (right bars). We observed however a high drop down in the last and 3rd step. In this step the system suggests/recommends documents, making a match between the author name in the document and the name of the user, and the platform requires the users to confirm/claim the authorship (i.e. the user can claim the documents, like papers, as the author and they will appear in the user profile).

As depicted in the area surrounded by the green circle in Figure 27 there is a specific group of users highlighted by a green circle. These users were asked to confirm whether they were the authors of some suggested documents. The data shows that none of the users in this group confirmed that they were the authors of the suggested documents. However, it's important to note that 33.33% of the users in the group chose to skip the question and did not provide an answer to the claiming prompt.

FIGURE 27 - CHART SHOWING THE AUTHORSHIP CLAIM DURING ONBOARDING

We found this an unusual metric indicating that none of the recommended documents matched the user's name. Upon further investigation, we discovered that this was caused by a technical bug and poor user experience in the claim process. The system was supposed to search for documents whose authors had a name similar to the user's, but the bug prevented the search results from being displayed, making it difficult for users to confirm their authorship.

To improve this, we first fixed the technical bug. Then, to enhance the user experience, we made the process of claiming authorship simpler by removing a secondary button in the document preview and changing the label of the main button that confirms the user's choice. This means that if the user is the author of the suggested documents, they only need to click on the "I'm the author" button and then the "Done" button. If they are not the author, they simply need to click the "Done" button. The image below illustrates the changes made to the interface showing the difference before and after.

FIGURE 28 - BEFORE (LEFT) AND AFTER (RIGHT) - WITH CHANGES TO THE CLAIM BUTTON

Therefore we have noticed changes in the Funnel by updating it and monitoring the new actions that users take.

The updated version of the funnel is shown in a green circle in Figure 29. From this updated version, we have noticed that 100% of users who have completed the initial steps were able to successfully complete the final three steps, which involved either confirming or skipping the process of claiming authorship.

FIGURE 29 - REGISTRATION/ONBOARDING FUNNEL WITH SUCCESS IN AUTHORSHIP CLAIM

3.4 User Satisfaction Questionnaire

A last component of Task 3.6 was the preparation of a final user satisfaction questionnaire (USQ). The goal of this activity was not to evaluate the usability of the platform interface, but rather to obtain an initial measure of how the users are satisfied with the platform and some specific aspects of it. Therefore the goal of this activity was to measure the attitude of the user toward the services of GoTriple and toward the platform as a whole. However as we noted in the introduction, the delays in the release of key components and the impacts this has had on the user engagement, has very likely had an effect on the completion of the questionnaire, with only 6 respondents at the time of writing. These responses are not enough to derive insights at this stage through statistical analysis, although we collected some positive feedback from the open questions e.g. “Some things have to be improved, but the idea is great”, with also feedback on how to improve the platform e.g. “All pretty nice, just the search function ‘after’ the ‘first’ search is still clunky on how to re-do or change the search”. Moreover we can consider that the results of the ReachOut campaign (which was done as additional work beyond the DOW) also report some insights into user satisfaction. It is however important to note that the user satisfaction questionnaire has been created with a view to use it well beyond the funding period, and it is indeed the plan for the WP leader to continue monitoring the results after March 2023, within the framework of the GoTriple Memorandum of Understanding.

The USQ was developed between the months of August and October 2022 and it was made available for completion to the user at the end of November 2022. Users arriving on the platform can access the USQ directly from the homepage of GoTriple by clicking on a “Your feedback” button, which contains a link to the USQ. The USQ in itself is a google form, and is available at the following URL: <https://forms.gle/h5zX5xvc3Gs5z6AD8>. This solution allows both users registered with an account as well as more casual users (those using GoTriple for discovery without an account) to fill in the questionnaire. This will also allow us to understand if there is any difference in satisfaction between these two different user groups.

In developing the USQ we aimed at approaching this for building a solution which would remain usable beyond the project funding. Indeed, although in this deliverable we report on the USQ structure, the plan is for the USQ to be a permanent feature for measuring satisfaction. Therefore, a key achievement of this part of the task is indeed having established a long term solution for measuring satisfaction.

FIGURE 30 - THE USQ IS ACCESSIBLE DIRECTLY FROM THE GOTRIPLE HOMEPAGE TO FACILITATE COMPLETION

The structure of the USQ is as follows. An initial set of questions asks general demographics, including: 1) “the type of users” (e.g. researchers, NGOs, policy makers etc.) reflecting what is asked at the time of user registration; 2) whether the user is a social scientist, a humanist, both of these options or if the respondent prefer not to say; 3) lastly in the initial part of the USQ a question asks about how the user got to know about GoTriple, for how long they have been a GoTriple user and whether they have an account in GoTriple (see Figure 31). This last set of questions is especially important as it tells if the user has been with the platform for some time (and it is thus better placed to evaluate satisfaction) and it allows us to distinguish users with or without an account.

How long have you been a user of GoTriple?

This is my first access

Less than 2 weeks

2 weeks to a month

A month to 3 months

3 months to 6 months

More than 6 months

Do you currently have an account/profile in GoTriple?

Yes

No

FIGURE 31 - THE USQ QUESTIONS ON HOW LONG PARTICIPANTS HAVE BEEN USERS

Next, the USQ proposes a set of questions for measuring satisfaction for a number of key aspects of GoTriple. It includes first a general section asking about general satisfaction of GoTriple as a whole and whether GoTriple met the user expectations. This is then followed by a set of likert scales asking in more detail about how easy it is to use the platform (see Figure 32) and two sets of likert scales (one of which is presented in Figure 33) about the satisfaction toward specific features and services offered.

Tell us if you agree or disagree with the following statements. With GoTriple:

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Unsure	Agree	Strongly Agree	Not Applicable
It is easy to formulate a search query	<input type="radio"/>					
It is easy to identify relevant literature	<input type="radio"/>					
It is easy to conduct a visual search	<input type="radio"/>					
Pages are loading reasonably fast	<input type="radio"/>					
The contents are clear to understand	<input type="radio"/>					

FIGURE 32 - THE USQ LIKERT SCALE ON HOW EASY IT IS TO USE THE PLATFORM

I am satisfied about:

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Unsure	Agree	Strongly Agree	Non Applicable/not used
The registration process	<input type="radio"/>					
The knowledge map	<input type="radio"/>					
The streamgraph	<input type="radio"/>					
The dashboards	<input type="radio"/>					
The icons	<input type="radio"/>					
The general search	<input type="radio"/>					
The languages features	<input type="radio"/>					
The user profile	<input type="radio"/>					
The annotation tool	<input type="radio"/>					
The Trust Building System	<input type="radio"/>					
The recommender system	<input type="radio"/>					

FIGURE 33- ONE OF THE SETS OF THE THE USQ QUESTIONS ON SATISFACTION

A final set of questions asks whether the users are likely to recommend GoTriple to colleagues and whether they will return to the platform. Moreover, each block of specific questions about satisfaction include open questions e.g. “Please feel free to provide us with some comments about any of your answers above”, to allow the user to report on additional issues not covered by the scales or to provide more details about their answers.

The questionnaire is quite compact and allows for an easy and quick completion. This is done by design as the goal is not to overburden the user with too many questions, concentrating on key aspects of the satisfaction. The informed consent is collected at the very beginning of the questionnaire.

4 ADDITIONAL ACTIVITIES

A set of additional activities were carried out as part of T3.6. The goals for these are varied and include capturing errors or bugs from the generic user (i.e. those who are not participating directly in any user testing), organising the usability issues that are identified in order to take action and communicate, with developers and the wider community, the work done around the design and the usability.

4.1 Bug Reporting

Finding bugs and errors is an important component of improving how users can take advantage of the platform and to improve their capacity to achieve their desired goals. However, finding bugs is not always related with evaluating the usability of the interface, as indeed bugs may arise from the malfunction of the underlying software rather than from issues with the design and the interface. However, a bug may have an impact on aspects such as the efficiency of achieving goals or the ease of use of the platform. As part of the work for this task, we have additionally created an initial bug reporting questionnaire, which has stayed live from the release of the Beta version in early 2022, until December 2022. The questionnaire reporting option was available to users directly on the GoTriple Beta interface where a clearly visible 'bug' icon and a pop-up message invites users to report any bugs they find. The icon linked to a google form questionnaire. This form also allowed capturing input from the GoTriple Beta casual users which are not directly involved in any specific testing session. From December 2022, the bug reporting questionnaire has been replaced with a more scalable solution based on Jira³, which allows a more systematic tracking of reports and has a more efficient ticketing system. This change also responds to one of the usability issues discussed earlier in the qualitative results section.

The interim Bug reporting questionnaire was organised in four sections according to the ABCD usability approach [9]. An online ABCD form provides a mechanism to support remote user feedback of any issues encountered, and a means for reflection to be incorporated into the feedback process by facilitating the user to document the retrospective recording of insights. This provides a structure to better understand the context in which a potential bug or error arose and also to understand what the user was trying to achieve and if they could envision a potential solution to the problem. This structured approach to bug reporting allows also to

³ Jira is a software that allows to track issues, manage projects, and automate workflows.

potentially link reported bugs with any usability issue. The ABCD questionnaire we devised was as follows:

A => The 'Antecedent' context

- Question for the user: What were you trying to do with GoTriple?

B => The problem 'Barrier'?

- Question for the user: What was the issue/problem you came across?

C => The 'Consequence' for the user?

- Question for the user: What was the consequence of this?

D => What development or decision is needed?

- Question for the user: Do you have any suggestions for fixing the problem?

The questions were offered as open fields where users were encouraged to provide as many details as they could on the bug they have encountered. Additionally, the form included the option for the user to upload a screenshot and provide any additional relevant information. Below is the example of a problem reported, which connects to a potential usability issue (the possibility to open a discovered paper in a new tab of the browser). Most importantly, the example shows the kind of detail we can obtain with an ABCD online form giving contextual information, details about the activity, the problem encountered and a potential solution. This solution allowed the capture of 44 bugs/reports, which were actioned upon by the GoTriple technical partners.

TABLE 2. - EXAMPLE OF A RECEIVED BUG REPORT, VIA THE ABCD FORM

A	B	C	D
Find publications on English as a Foreign Language to get an overview of recent issues in the topic.	I would like to be able to open a document in a new tab or page so that I don't lose my spot when I come back, but right clicking doesn't give the option for some reason and left clicking directly opens the entry.	Since right clicking doesn't give me the option to open in a new tab, I end up coming back to the top of the list and having to click through the pages to find where I left off.	Have the entries automatically open in a new tab.

Moving forward and looking at the sustainability of the bug reporting process beyond the funding period, in December 2022 the project partners have taken the decision to integrate a

Jira “bug reporting/issue reporting” widget on the GoTriple interface. Users can click on the “report an issue” button which is clearly visible from the interface, and the widget will open with a simple form to complete (see Figure 34). This will create a report and a ticket and it is an approach more scalable and systematic than an ad-hoc questionnaire (which was created indeed as an interim solution, whilst exploring a long-term solution). It also has the advantage of allowing the user to do the reporting whilst staying on the GoTriple platform (whereas the questionnaire was a google form and thus required the user to move on another browser to make a report).

FIGURE 34 - THE NEW ISSUE REPORTING, ADDED IN DECEMBER 2022, WHICH IS FULLY INTEGRATED ON THE GO TRIPLE INTERFACE

4.2 Trello Board

Trello was introduced in the usability workflow to enable remote collaboration to address the findings of qualitative user testing. We introduced this technology to pass emerging issues encountered during the qualitative user testing (conducted by Abertay) to the design team (located at Net7), see Figure 35. Trello is a web-based project management tool that empowers agile teams to manage project, workflow, or task tracking. We chose Trello because it allows us to visually organise the workflow and is easy for others on the team to understand what exactly needs to be done.

The established workflow starts when the results of the usability testing are available after analysis of the tests conducted with end-users. The usability issues encountered during the

analysis are carefully documented also with screenshots to show the exact places on the interface that needed attention by the design teams. The issues are then placed on the TRIPLE - UX/UI activities window in Trello, with relative indication of details about the issue. From there the design team can establish their own workflow (see Figure 36) to show the identified requirements that have been approved (i.e. usability issues which need to be investigated and addressed in the next or a future update), done (i.e. usability issues which have been solved) or rejected (e.g. these could be issues which have emerged during testing but are due features already planned but not currently available, or issues which are not related with the interface design as such but due to software errors).

FIGURE 35 - UX/UI VIEW OF THE TRELLO BOARD WHERE THE USABILITY ISSUES ARE REPORTED

FIGURE 36 - UX/UI VIEW OF THE TRELLO BOARD WHERE THE USABILITY ISSUES ARE APPROVED, DONE OR REJECTED

5 CONCLUSIONS

The work for Task 3.6 focused on the evaluation of core aspects of the usability of the GoTriple platform Interface. Overall the work conducted for Task 3.6 has given important and valuable insights for improving the final design of the GoTriple platform ahead of the final release and the end of funding. Through the evaluation work activities adopted (qualitative/quantitative) we were able to capture a number of issues impacting on the capacity of the user to achieve their intended discovery goals with the platform, or impacting on the general user experience of the interface. This deliverable (*D3.6 User Evaluation - Final*) has consequently detailed the methodology adopted for the evaluation and has shown some key examples of the results obtained, including changes, improvements and redesign of interface elements. With the submission of D3.6 the cycle of the user research for GoTriple also completes.

Usability and user experience are continuous processes of improvements and while several issues were identified during this evaluation, this is a picture at the current stage of the platform release at the moment of writing. As GoTriple will continue after the funding period as an OPERAS service, there will be new updates and improvements and we expect to see a much more extensive use of the platform by SSH scholars and other users across Europe. Consequently, more work will need to be done, on a continuous basis to improve the interface as more users will join and start using GoTriple in their workflow. Testing the usability will need to remain a constant aspect for the entire life-time of the GoTriple platform for the future. The user satisfaction questionnaire which was created during T3.6 will remain available for the foreseeable future, allowing the GoTriple managers to gauge potential emerging issues around satisfaction. It could be considered that for capturing some usability issues in the future a

further self-completion questionnaire could also be adopted, alongside the conduction of additional qualitative testing. The quantitative funnels also will remain in place for the future to monitor the onboarding of users.

Nonetheless, it appears from the observations and the work that we made with the users during this last period of the project that the current interface design of GoTriple is already capable of meeting the expectations of the users, despite it will still need to receive some improvements. For example, one of our testers gave the following comment at the end of the testing session: *[The Interface] 'It's pretty intuitive, it's not like it's clunky or difficult to operate. I think it definitely would be useful for my work.'* Another participant to the Task's research stated *'The search feature looks functional and provides different types of results, including projects, and I find it useful.'* These are just some examples of positive comments, which are a testament of significant work done to deliver a digital solution that supports the user to achieve their intended goals and needs. The time and effort spent to work with users during the entire WP3 was therefore well invested and delivered significant returns for the platform and the users.

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